

Polarographic Determination of Formation Constants of the Mixed-ligand Complexes of Cadmium(II) and Lead(II) with Thiosulphate and Tartrate

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The mixed-ligand complexes of Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} with thiosulphate as a primary ligand and tartrate as a secondary ligand have been investigated polarographically. Two mixed-ligand complexes are formed with each metal ion and the overall formation constants are $\log \beta_{1,2} = 5.95$ and 5.55 and $\log \beta_{2,1} = 5.80$ and 5.54 for Cd^{II} and Pb^{II}, respectively, at 30° and $\mu = 1.0$ M (NaClO₄). The negative value of $\log \beta_{1,1}$ indicates the absence of the complexes 1 : 1 : 1 in both the systems.

THE literature reveals the polarographic behaviour of Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} in either thiosulphate¹⁻³ or tartrate⁴⁻⁶ solutions. Mixed-ligand complexes of Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} with thiosulphate as the primary ligand have been investigated previously^{2,3,7,8}. No information is available describing the polarographic reduction or complex equilibria of both the metal ions in a mixture of thiosulphate and tartrate. The present study was undertaken to find an evidence for the presence of any probable ternary complexes formed by the interaction of Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} with thiosulphate - tartrate mixtures.

Experimental

Polarograms were recorded with a Tacussel PRG 5 polarograph (3-electrode) in conjunction with TVIIGD plugin and EPLI recorder.

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and dissolved in double-distilled water. Triton X-100 was used as a maximum-suppressor. The ionic strength was maintained at 1.0 M with NaClO₄. The polarograms were recorded after deaeration of the test solution with purified nitrogen at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$. Saturated calomel electrode (SCE) with sodium chloride was used instead of potassium chloride to prevent precipitation in the perchlorate medium. The concentration of the metal ion as nitrate was fixed at 5×10^{-4} M. The capillary had the following characteristics: $t = 4.11$ s, $m = 2.10$ mg s⁻¹, $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.08$ mg^{2/3} s^{1/6} in 0.1 M KCl solution (open circuit) and a mercury head of 55 cm.

Results and Discussion

Simple metal complexes: The stepwise formation constants for the simple (binary) thiosulphate and tartrate complexes of Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} were first determined to obtain data under conditions which

are identical with those used in the mixed (ternary) complex studies. The polarographic reduction of Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} in the presence of these ligands (individually) was found reversible and diffusion-controlled as indicated from logarithmic analysis plots of the waves and from the effect of the mercury height on the reduction current, respectively.

In the case of sodium thiosulphate (Ts) the concentration of the ligand was varied from 0.005 to 0.33 M. The relation between $E_{1/2}$ values and $\log [Ts]$ (12 solution) exhibits linear portions with breaks (Fig. 1) indicating the formation of 1 : 1,

Fig. 1. $-E_{1/2}$ as function of $\log$ [thiosulphate] for the lead-thiosulphate - tartrate system: (a) 0.00, (b) 0.06 and (c) 0.15 M tartrate.

1 : 2 and 1 : 3 metal-ligand complexes. The formation constants were determined (Table 1). Both the number of ligands bound to the metal ion and the overall formation constants were computed by the means of Lingane's treatment⁹ of the polarographic data. The values are in close agreement with the published values¹⁻⁸, allowing for the ionic strength and the electrolytes used by other workers.

It is worthy to mention that some reports^{2,8} indicated that the $E_{1/2} - \log [X]$ plot is a smooth curve without break. In that case, the procedure developed by DeFord and Hume¹⁰ given by the equation,

$$F_o(X) = \text{antilog} \left(-\frac{0.435 nF}{RT} \Delta E_{1/2} + \log \frac{I_M}{I_C} \right)$$

was followed. In this equation, $-0.435 nF/RT$ is the reciprocal slope of the polarographic wave, $\Delta E_{1/2}$ is the difference between the $E_{1/2}$ values at $[X]=0$ and $[X] \neq 0$, and I_M and I_C are the diffusion current constants of the simple and complexed metal ion, respectively. It is assumed that the reason for the smooth curve is due to the small differences in the formation constants of the complexes¹¹. The constants are affected by the experimental conditions, viz. ionic strength, supporting electrolyte, solvent and concentration range of the ligand. Consequently, difference in the shape of the $E_{1/2} - \log [X]$ plot may be noticed.

In the investigation of the metal-tartrate complexes, *d*-tartaric acid (Tar.) concentration was varied from 0.03 to 0.30 *M* and the pH was kept constant at 5.0-5.2. From the effect of pH on the $E_{1/2}$ values, it was found that the reduction of Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} is pH-independent in the pH range 4.5-7.0 and 4.5-9.5, respectively, in presence of constant tartaric acid concentration (0.2 *M*) and $\mu=1.0$ *M* NaClO₄. The $E_{1/2} - \log [\text{Tar.}]$ plots were also linear with breaks corresponding to 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal-ligand complexes. The values of the formation constant are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Cd²⁺ AND Pb²⁺ BINARY COMPLEXES WITH THIOSULPHATE AND TARTRATE

System	Formation constant
Cd-Ts	log β_{10} = 4.00
	log β_{20} = 5.18
	log β_{30} = 6.70
Cd-Tar.	log β_{01} = 2.17
	log β_{02} = 3.23
Pb-Ts	log β_{10} = 3.63
	log β_{20} = 4.83
	log β_{30} = 6.70
Pb-Tar.	log β_{01} = 2.57
	log β_{02} = 4.23

Mixed-ligand systems : Schaap and McMasters¹² pointed out that in a system in which two or more ligands are present, mixed-ligand complexes should be formed in preference to simple complexes

whenever $\beta_{MX_i} [X]^i \sim \beta_{MY_j} [Y]^j$. A shift in half-wave potential, at a given concentration of both the ligands to more negative value than that for either of the simple systems at the same metal, indicates the formation of mixed-ligand complexes. Several equilibria exist and hence, the DeFord and Hume¹⁰ expression for $F_o(X)$ may be extended to give a new function $F_{oo}(X, Y)$ given by

$$F_{oo}(X, Y) = \text{antilog} \left(-\frac{0.435 nF}{RT} \Delta E_{1/2} + \log \frac{I_M}{I_C} \right) \\ = A + B[X] + C[X]^2 + D[X]^3$$

where,

$$A = \beta_{00} + \beta_{01}[Y] + \beta_{02}[Y]^2 + \beta_{03}[Y]^3, \\ B = \beta_{10} + \beta_{11}[Y] + \beta_{12}[Y]^2, \\ C = \beta_{20} + \beta_{21}[Y], \text{ and} \\ D = \beta_{30},$$

the β_{ij} values being the overall stability constants of the system (for simple complexes i or $j=0$).

The values of all the stability constants in the equations above can be obtained if the half-wave potentials and diffusion currents of at least two series of solutions are measured, each series at a constant concentration of Y (tartrate in our case) and increasing concentrations of X (thiosulphate). The formation constants of the simple systems have already been determined. The constants B , C and D can be obtained from the functions,

$$F_{10} = \frac{F_{00} - A}{[X]} = B + C[X] + D[X]^2$$

$$F_{20} = \frac{F_{10} - B}{[X]} = C + D[X]$$

$$F_{30} = \frac{F_{20} - C}{[X]} = D$$

by an extrapolation to zero ligand concentration of the plots of the corresponding functions. The constant A can be obtained in the same way from F_{00} or from the stability constants of the metal-tartrate system. The same is true for the constant D , i.e. from the F_{30} vs $[X]$ plot or directly from the value $D = \beta_{30}$. The constants A and D obtained graphically or numerically agree satisfactorily with the values obtained from the simple metal-tartrate and metal-thiosulphate systems, respectively.

Metal-thiosulphate-tartrate systems : Solutions containing 0.5 *mM* Cd²⁺, 0.09 *M* tartaric acid and the requisite amount of NaClO₄ and NaOH (to maintain pH=6.5-6.7 and $\mu=1.0$ *M*) were polarographed at varying concentrations of thiosulphate ions (5.0-0.12 *M*). In each case the single well-defined wave had a slope of 30 ± 1 mV for the plots of $-E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log i/(i_d - i)$ indicating that the reduction is reversible involving two electrons. The direct proportionality of the diffusion current to the effective height of mercury column indicates that the solution is entirely diffusion-controlled. The same results were obtained when tartarate

concentration was kept constant at 0.15 M. The same procedure was done with Pb^{2+} instead of Cd^{2+} but the tartarate concentration was kept constant at 0.06 M in one set and 0.15 M in the other set of solutions.

A shift in $E_{1/2}$ potential to more negative side with increasing thiosulphate ion concentration was observed in the four series. This shift in presence of tartrate is greater in magnitude to that obtained in absence of tartrate (Fig. 1). This indicates mixed-ligand complex formation by tartrate and thiosulphate ions. The F_i function is represented by the plots shown in Fig. 2. The values of A, B, C, D and β_{11} are given in Table 2. Both Cd^{2+} and Pb^{2+} gave negative values of β_{11} indicating the absence of $\text{M}[(\text{Ts})(\text{Tar})]^{2-}$ complexes in the solutions. A negative value was also observed for $\log \beta_{21}$ at the lower concentrations of tartrate.

It has been claimed that the experimental stability constants of mixed-ligand complexes are higher than the statistically calculated constants for electrostatic and steric reasons^{12,13}. Following the procedure of Watters and DeWitt¹⁴, the

Fig. 2. Plots of F_{10} vs [thiosulphate] for cadmium-thiosulphate-tartrate system at $[\text{Tar.}] = 0.15 \text{ M}$.

TABLE 2—MIXED FORMATION CONSTANTS

System	$\log A$	$\log B$	$\log C$	$\log D$	$\log \beta_{11}$	$\log \beta_{21}$	$\log \beta_{31}$
Temp. = 30°, $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M}$ (NaClO_4)							
Od ^{II} - Ts - Tar.							
(a) 0.09 M (Tar.)	1.44	3.34	5.08	6.28	—	5.95	—
(b) 0.15 M (Tar.)	1.78	3.76	5.36	6.46	—	—	5.80
Pb ^{II} - Ts - Tar.							
(a) 0.06 M (Tar.)	1.91	3.55	4.66	6.00	—	—	—
(b) 0.15 M (Tar.)	2.56	3.87	5.08	6.70	—	5.55	5.54

predicted values for the complexation constants for Cd^{II} are $10^{4.96}$ and $10^{4.95}$ for the 1:1:2 and 1:2:1 complexes, respectively, as compared to these observed, i.e. $10^{5.95}$ and $10^{5.80}$; the enhancement seen in these are $10^{1.09}$ and $10^{0.82}$, respectively. The predicted stability constants of Pb^{II} mixed-ligand complexes are $10^{5.53}$ and $10^{5.11}$ for the 1:1:2 and 1:2:1 complexes against $10^{5.55}$ and $10^{5.54}$, with enhancement factors of $10^{0.02}$ and $10^{0.43}$, respectively.

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